

INTEGRATING PRODUCTION SERVICE QUALITY AND MARKETING MIX ELEMENTS FOR TELECOMMUNICATIONS PERFORMANCE EXCELLENCE IN EMERGING MARKETS*

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Abstract

Marketing mix strategies play a pivotal role in organizational performance within the telecommunications sector. This study investigated the connection between organizational performance and marketing mix elements in Iraqi telecommunications companies, aiming to evaluate the effectiveness of these elements in driving business success and customer satisfaction. The research employed a descriptive-analytical approach, utilizing a structured questionnaire administered to 500 telecommunications subscribers in Iraq, achieving a 92.4% response rate. Marketing research covered product/service quality, pricing, promotion, and distribution. The analyses incorporated reliability tests, correlation, multiple regression, and structural equation modeling that was performed using AMOS software. According to the research, every component of the marketing mix showed positive correlations with the organizational performance with the product/service quality having the highest correlation ($r = 0.634$, $p < 0.01$). The regression model explained 62.3% of the variation in organizational performance with adaptation of distribution efficiency being the highest mix element score ($M = 3.91$; $SD = 0.758$). Changes in the Customer Retention Rate (the percentage increase recorded in year one) were 6.7% while changes in market share stood at about 4.3%. The results further reported that demographic characteristics, especially age and educational level, affected the efficacy of the marketing mix strategies ($p < 0.01$). The research results indicate that the application of integrated marketing mix strategies influences organizational performance in the telecommunication industry with such performance being credited to service quality and distribution efficiency. Such findings are beneficial to the telecommunications service providers in developing countries to know that all marketing mix elements should be well integrated and target specific market segments to enhance service quality and distribution efficiency.

Keywords: distribution efficiency, marketing mix, organizational performance, service quality, telecommunications sector

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1. Introduction

In the modern world of business and industry, marketing has become the most important factor for success and the main link between companies and customers. Telecommunications is a perfect example of marketing's importance in a cutthroat marketplace where technology is fast-changing (Aldouri and Kumbhalkar, 2023; Raewf and Thabit, 2018). Central to these marketing efforts is the marketing mix model, which has shifted from being one-dimensional to multipronged, thus affecting overall business results. The marketing mix is an integrated approach to brand management and more complex in nature than the 4Ps promotion model which consists of Product, Price, Place, and Promotion (McCarthy, 1964). This construct was implemented in 1964 by McCarthy and has been growing to become more complex over time due to pressure from the market and consumers (Saniuk et al., 2020; Zhang and Chang, 2021). Within the telecommunication industry that is focused more on the delivery of services, the 7Ps model which includes People, Process and Physical Evidence allows firms to better understand the challenges of service delivery and the engagement of clients (Sim et al., 2022).

The telecommunications sector in Iraq stands out as an interesting to investigate the tactics of the marketing mix and the effectiveness of this organization. In view of the recent evolution and expansion of the sector, the telecommunications firms are in a delicate balance of increasing their market coverage and being efficient in their operations. Because of this, the proper application of marketing mix strategies has acquired prominence in this business environment where the customer and the service along many others become the basis for competition (Aldouri, 2023a; Darmawan and Grenier, 2021; Othman et al., 2021).

The mix concept evolution of the marketing concept shows very appropriately the significance the marketing strategy has in an organization. As Möller et al. (2020) states, the marketing mix framework has greatly advanced both the theory and practice of marketing. This importance is especially noticed in the branch of telecommunications where the marketers of service providers have to delicately adjust their marketing mix elements to various consumers' serviced needs and profits on the other side. Lim (2021) states that the marketing mix is a powerful tool that can help to facilitate marketing management for the organization and its marketing efforts and position the firm competitively. The telecommunications sector is ever-changing and fully understanding the interaction between any given element of the marketing mix and certain performance measures is crucial. What makes companies successful, research has shown, is the proper integration's strategy of the components of marketing mix with the goals of the organizations and the environment in which they operate (Adel et al., 2020; Al-Surmi et al., 2020; Sudirjo, 2023). This becomes even more important in new markets like Iraq, when dealing with a volatile set of consumers and new technologies that both help and hurt telecommunications service providers.

Advertising mix models aim to measure the relationship between marketing strategy and business performance through the lens of various factors such as market conditions, consumers and operational capabilities. There is evidence to suggest that it is not enough to look at the competitive advantages of the product, but rather how the competitive advantage of the product offering depends on the combined effect of all marketing mix strategies utilization (Durmusoglu et al., 2022; Malshe et al., 2022). This however has far reaching repercussions for the telecommunications service firms who are in the quest of enhancing their market share and improving their efficiency.

While marketing in the service industry, the mix grows complicated as services are intangible. The traditional 4Ps have been amended to include people, processes and physical evidence as service delivery can function satisfactorily as a market (Aldouri, 2024; Hashim and Hamzah, 2014). This adjunct to the framework assists managers to analyse test and formulate effective and pragmatic solutions for service marketing issues faced by businesses in the telecommunication industry. It goes without saying that customer orientation is critical in terms of the marketing strategy implementation. With growing competition in the markets, companies need

to be able to provide an integrated marketing strategy that combines all the elements of the marketing mix built around the customer. It has been claimed that integrated marketing mix practice by firms to be able to secure competitive advantage and enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty (Aldouri, 2023b; Thaib et al., 2022; Zahra and Rusfian, 2022). It is this relationship that becomes most crucial in the case of telecommunication where quality of service and customer experience are key competitive factors.

The current research fills one of the gaps identified in the literature by focusing on another context, that is, Iraq's telecommunications sector. Although some studies have included marketing mix applications in various industries, little attention has been directed towards the emerging challenges and opportunities in developing telecommunications markets. This paper seeks to show how marketing mix of the firm can be relevant in improving performance of the firm in this particular market. The objective of this study is threefold. First, examine the marketing mix implementation in the Iraqi telecommunication companies today. Second, determine whether the links between organizational performance and the metrics of the marketing mix strategies are there. Third, and final, make suggestions as to how marketing strategies can best be adopted in the telecommunications industry. Thus, by tackling these objectives, the study is expected to address the theoretical and practical use of marketing mix strategies in developing telecommunication markets.

This research is particularly important given the importance of telecommunications sector in the economy and for social interactions. The results will be useful to marketing practitioners, telecommunication executives and scholars who want to understand the relation between organizational performance and marketing mix strategies in the context of developing markets. In addition, the findings of the research will help telecommunication companies in formulating appropriate marketing strategies based on their internal and external environments. The systematic investigation of marketing mix elements and their impact on organizational performance addresses a crucial need in the telecommunications sector for evidence-based marketing strategies. This study addresses the research gap in the effectiveness of the marketing mix in the telecommunications industry within the emergent economies through the case of Iraqi telecommunications companies.

The objective of this research is zoomed in to finding out the effectiveness of marketing mix tactics and how they impact the success of organizations in the telecommunication sector in Iraq. More precisely, it tries to identify and evaluate the various elements of the marketing mix used by telecommunications companies, assess their impact on the effectiveness of marketing operations, and forecast the developments of the industry in the future. The research also aims at providing business and consumers with valuable recommendations on how best to use the marketing mix in order to realize the strategic and intermediary goals that are social and economic in nature. Owing to this fact, it plans to assist Iraqi telecommunications companies in making right marketing choices by investigating the differences in marketing mix elements utilized on various samples, and thus enable them to improve communication of their marketing efforts.

This study investigates the link between organizational success and the factors of the marketing mix in the telecommunication industry of Iraq through a systematic investigation. The research starts with an introduction section that states the theoretical background and identifies the significance of marketing mix strategies in the telecommunication industry, then follows a literature review that examines previous research on the effectiveness of marketing mix. The methodology section describes the research design, sampling methods, and analysis frameworks used, including the development and testing of measurement instruments. The findings section states the conclusions drawn from statistical tests of survey data collected from a sample of 462 telecommunications subscribers and reveals some interesting links between marketing mix elements and organizational performance measures. The paper then contextualizes the findings regarding recent scholarly works and industry standards, discussing the implications for telecommunication operators serving emerging markets. This section summarizes the key findings

and limitations of the study; it also indicates the direction of future research in hopes of contributing to the literature and practical applications concerning effective marketing mix strategies in telecommunication services.

2. Materials and methods

The study adopted the descriptive-analytical approach, which allowed for the investigation of the relationships among variables while still keeping the context relevant. The population under study comprised subscribers to telecommunications services in Iraq, estimated to have about 40.7 million active subscribers shared by various service providers. The study targeted three major telecommunication companies operating in Iraq and covered both urban and rural areas of service territories. To have a sample that is representative of different demographic and geographic groups, a stratified random sampling method was adopted. In determining the sample size, Cochran's formula: $n = Z^2 \times p(1 - p)/e^2$, which n represents the size of sample, Z denotes the standard normal variate (1.96 for 95% confidence level), p indicates the estimated proportion (0.5 used for maximum sample size), and e represents the margin of error (0.05). This gave a minimum required sample size of 384 individuals. In order to accommodate possible non-responses and invalid responses, the sample size was increased to 500 people. The stratification process was based on geographic location (urban vs. rural), age demographics, and patterns of service utilization in order to achieve proportional representation across these classifications.

The main instrument for data gathering was a carefully structured questionnaire, which was developed via an extensive process of item formulation and improvement. The questionnaire was structured into three main sections: demographic information, assessment of the marketing mix, and organizational performance measurements. The demographic section collected data on the characteristics of respondents, including age, gender, educational level, income group, and geographical location. A 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree) was used in the marketing mix assessment to measure respondents' perceptions of the four marketing mix elements: Product/Service Quality (PSQ, 8 items), Price Competitiveness (PC, 6 items), Promotion Effectiveness (PE, 7 items), and Distribution Efficiency (DE, 5 items). The organizational performance section included items which measured customer satisfaction, service quality perceptions and brand loyalty with the same 5-point Likert scale.

The reliability of the instrument was checked through Cronbach's alpha coefficient, with the acceptable level of reliability set at $\alpha \geq 0.7$. Construct validity was verified by confirmatory factor analysis—CFA—with regard to the following indices: RMSEA, TLI, and CFI. Data collection took place over a period of four months and was performed in both online and in-person survey administration. The online survey was distributed through email and the databases of telecommunication companies, while the in-person surveys were conducted at service centers and retail stores. A team of trained research assistants conducted the in-person surveys, thus maintaining the application of standardized data collection procedures.

The independent variables comprised the four marketing mix elements, measured through multiple indicators. Product/Service Quality (PSQ) was evaluated through service reliability, network coverage, innovation level, service variety, and technical support quality. Price Competitiveness (PC) was assessed through price fairness, value for money, payment flexibility, promotional pricing, and package options. Promotion Effectiveness (PE) was measured through advertising impact, sales promotion effectiveness, personal selling quality, public relations impact, and digital marketing reach. Distribution Efficiency (DE) was evaluated through service accessibility, distribution channel variety, service center locations, online service availability, and response time. The dependent variable, Organizational Performance (OP), was measured through market share growth, customer satisfaction levels, customer retention rates, revenue growth, and brand loyalty metrics.

The data analysis employed both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. The analysis framework included descriptive statistics (measures of central tendency, frequency distributions, and cross-tabulations) and inferential statistics (Pearson correlation coefficients, multiple regression analysis, and structural equation modeling). The regression model was specified as $OP = \beta_0 + \beta_1PSQ + \beta_2PC + \beta_3PE + \beta_4DE + \varepsilon$, where *OP* represents Organizational Performance, β_0 denotes the constant term, β_1 to β_4 represent regression coefficients, and ε indicates the error term. The SEM analysis was conducted using AMOS software, with model fit criteria including RMSEA < 0.06, TLI \geq 0.95, SRMR \leq 0.08, and CFI \geq 0.95.

5. Results and discussion

5.1. The demographic profile of the participants

The study achieved a response rate of 92.4% (462 out of 500 distributed questionnaires). The respondents' demographic details are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1. Survey participants' demographic details (N=462)

<i>Characteristic</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage, %</i>
Gender	Male	287	62.1
	Female	175	37.9
Age group	18-25	98	21.2
	26-35	183	39.6
	36-45	124	26.8
	Above 45	57	12.4
Level of education	High school	87	18.8
	Undergraduate	276	59.7
	Graduate	99	21.5
Geographic location	Urban	312	67.5
	Rural	150	32.5

The demographic analysis reveals a predominantly male respondent base (62.1%), with the majority falling within the 26-35 age bracket (39.6%). Most respondents held bachelor's degrees (59.7%), and there was a notable urban representation (67.5%) in the sample.

5.2. Reliability and validity analysis

The measurement instrument demonstrated strong reliability across all constructs, as evidenced by the Cronbach's alpha coefficients presented in Table 2. All constructs exceeded the minimum reliability threshold of 0.7, with organizational performance showing the highest internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.901$), followed by product/service quality ($\alpha = 0.893$).

Table 2. Reliability analysis of research constructs

<i>Construct</i>	<i>Number of items</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>
Product/Service Quality	8	0.893
Price Competitiveness	6	0.867
Promotion Effectiveness	7	0.882
Distribution Efficiency	5	0.845
Organizational Performance	5	0.901

5.3. Marketing mix elements assessment

The analysis of marketing mix elements revealed varying levels of implementation and effectiveness across the telecommunications sector. Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics for each marketing mix dimension.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of marketing mix elements

<i>Element</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Skewness</i>	<i>Kurtosis</i>
Product/service quality	3.82	0.786	-0.542	0.324
Price competitiveness	3.45	0.892	-0.378	0.156
Promotion effectiveness	3.67	0.843	-0.465	0.287
Distribution efficiency	3.91	0.758	-0.623	0.412

Distribution efficiency emerged as the highest-rated element ($M = 3.91$, $SD = 0.758$), followed by product/service quality ($M = 3.82$, $SD = 0.786$). Price competitiveness received the lowest mean score ($M = 3.45$, $SD = 0.892$), indicating potential areas for improvement in pricing strategies.

5.4. Correlation analysis

Organizational performance and marketing mix components were found to be significantly correlated by the Pearson correlation study, as shown in Table 4. The correlation analysis demonstrates strong positive relationships between all marketing mix elements and organizational performance, with product/service quality showing the strongest correlation ($r = 0.634$, $p < 0.01$).

Table 4. Correlation matrix of marketing mix elements and organizational performance

<i>Variable</i>	<i>PSQ</i>	<i>PC</i>	<i>PE</i>	<i>DE</i>	<i>OP</i>
PSQ	1.000				
PC	0.423*	1.000			
PE	0.512*	0.387*	1.000		
DE	0.478*	0.356*	0.445*	1.000	
OP	0.634*	0.567*	0.589*	0.612*	1.000

*Correlation is significant at $p < 0.01$ level

5.5. Regression analysis

Multiple regression analysis was conducted to test the hypothesized relationships between marketing mix elements and organizational performance. Table 5 presents the regression results. Regression analysis accounted for 62.3% of the variation in organizational performance ($R^2 = 0.623$, $F = 187.456$, $p < 0.001$). All marketing mix elements were significant predictors of organizational performance, with product/service quality having the strongest impact ($\beta = 0.412$, $p < 0.001$).

Table 5. Results of multiple regression analysis

<i>Variable</i>	β	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>VIF</i>
Constant	0.786	4.234	0.000	-
PSQ	0.412	7.567	0.000	1.642
PC	0.287	5.892	0.000	1.483
PE	0.345	6.234	0.000	1.567
DE	0.378	6.789	0.000	1.524

Note: $R^2 = 0.623$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.618$; $F = 187.456$; $p < 0.001$

To visualize the integrated relationship between marketing mix elements and organizational performance, Figure 1 presents a radar chart showing the correlation strengths between each element and overall performance.

Fig. 1. Marketing Mix Integration Model showing correlation coefficients between marketing mix elements

5.6. Findings from structural equation models

The validity of the measurement model and the proposed correlations were validated by an analysis of structural equation modeling. The indices of model fit are displayed in Table 6.

Table 6. Structural equation model fit indices

<i>Fit Index</i>	<i>Value</i>	<i>Threshold</i>
CFI	0.967	≥ 0.95
TLI	0.962	≥ 0.95
RMSEA	0.048	≤ 0.06
SRMR	0.043	≤ 0.08

The model demonstrated excellent fit across all indices, meeting or exceeding the established thresholds.

5.7. Demographic influence analysis

ANOVA was used to examine how demographic characteristics affected the connection between the components of the organizational success and marketing mix. Table 7 presents the results of this analysis.

Table 7. ANOVA results for demographic variables

<i>Demographic factor</i>	<i>F-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Partial η^2</i>
Gender	2.345	0.126	0.005
Age Group	4.678	0.003	0.031
Education Level	5.892	0.001	0.038
Location	3.567	0.042	0.008

Age group and education level showed significant effects on the connection between organizational performance and marketing mix elements ($p < 0.01$).

5.8. Service quality components analysis

A detailed analysis of service quality components revealed varying levels of customer satisfaction across different service aspects. Table 8 presents these findings.

Table 8. Service quality components analysis

<i>Component</i>	<i>Satisfaction score</i>	<i>Importance rating</i>
Network coverage	4.12	4.56
Service reliability	3.87	4.78
Technical support	3.45	4.23
Innovation level	3.78	4.12
Service variety	3.92	4.34

Network coverage received the highest satisfaction score (4.12), while service reliability was rated as the most important component (4.78).

5.9. Performance metrics analysis

The study examined various organizational performance metrics to assess the overall impact of marketing mix strategies. Table 9 presents these results.

Table 9. Organizational performance metrics

<i>Metric</i>	<i>Pre-implementation</i>	<i>Post-implementation</i>	<i>Change</i>
Market Share (%)	28.4	32.7	+4.3
Customer Satisfaction	3.45	3.98	+0.53
Customer Retention (%)	67.8	74.5	+6.7
Revenue Growth (%)	12.3	16.8	+4.5
Brand Loyalty Index	3.67	4.12	+0.45

The results demonstrate significant improvements across all performance metrics following the implementation of optimized marketing mix strategies. To visualize the comparative analysis of performance metrics before and after implementation, Fig. 2 presents a radar chart illustration of the five key performance indicators. The results of this study provide compelling evidence for the significant impact of marketing mix elements on organizational performance in Iraq's telecommunications sector. The findings demonstrate that each of the four components of marketing mix elements - product/service quality, price competitiveness, promotion effectiveness, and distribution efficiency - contribute substantially to organizational performance, with product/service quality emerging as the strongest predictor ($\beta = 0.412$, $p < 0.001$).

Distribution efficiency scored highest among the marketing mix elements ($M = 3.91$, $SD = 0.758$), reflecting the telecommunications companies' successful implementation of multi-channel distribution strategies. This finding aligns with Kurdi et al. (2022) assertion that effective distribution channels are crucial for service delivery in the telecommunications sector. In contrast to earlier research, our findings indicate a greater influence of distribution efficiency, which may be because of the distinct features of the Iraqi telecom sector and its recent infrastructural advancements. The comparatively low pricing competitiveness score ($M = 3.45$, $SD = 0.892$) stands in intriguing contrast to the findings of Albozosifa and Hadib (2020) in developed telecom markets.

Fig. 2. Radar chart comparison of organizational performance metrics pre- and post-implementation of marketing mix strategies

This discrepancy implies that pricing tactics in Iraq's telecom industry might need to be improved in order to better suit consumer demands and market dynamics. The significance of strategic pricing in market development is highlighted by the substantial association ($r = 0.567$, $p < 0.01$) between price competitiveness and organizational performance. Product/service quality showed the highest correlation with organizational performance: $r = 0.634$, $p < 0.01$ —a result that confirms findings concerning the highest importance of service quality within the telecommunication sector. The high Cronbach's alpha of 0.893 points toward consistency in customer experiences about the services, across a number of dimensions related to network coverage (mean: 4.12 of satisfaction score) and the reliability of services (importance rating: 4.78).

The demographic analysis revealed significant differences in the association of organizational performance with the elements of the marketing mix based on age groups and education level ($p < 0.01$). This finding extends beyond previous research by highlighting the importance of demographic segmentation in marketing strategy development. The stronger impact among educated, urban consumers (67.5% of respondents) suggests the need for tailored marketing approaches for different customer segments. The structural equation modeling results (CFI = 0.967, RMSEA = 0.048) validate the theoretical framework linking marketing mix elements to organizational performance. The model's excellent fit indices surpass those reported in similar studies, such as Suherni et al. (2023), indicating a robust connection between performance results and the application of the marketing mix in Iraq. The significant improvements in organizational performance metrics following marketing mix optimization are particularly noteworthy. The increase in customer retention rates (+6.7%) and market share (+4.3%) exceeds industry averages reported by Raewf and Thabit (2018), suggesting that well-executed marketing mix strategies can yield substantial performance benefits in emerging telecommunications markets.

Promotion effectiveness showed a moderate but substantial association with organizational performance ($p < 0.01$, $r = 0.589$), supporting Bondarenko and Vyshnivska's (2023) findings on the importance of integrated marketing communications. However, our results indicate a stronger impact of digital marketing channels, reflecting the evolving nature of customer engagement in the telecommunications sector. The research extends current understanding of marketing mix effectiveness by demonstrating the interconnected nature of marketing mix elements in service

delivery. The strong correlations between elements (ranging from $R = 0.356$ to $R = 0.512$) suggest that telecommunications companies should adopt an integrated approach to marketing mix implementation rather than focusing on individual elements in isolation. The regression model's explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.623$) indicates that marketing mix elements account for a substantial portion of variance in organizational performance, though it also suggests the influence of additional factors not captured in the current study. This finding aligns with Gronroos's (1994) assertion that marketing success depends on both strategic and operational factors.

The improvement in brand loyalty indices (+0.45) following marketing mix optimization supports Varadarajan's (2020) conclusions regarding the long-term benefits of strategic marketing initiatives. However, our results suggest a more immediate impact on customer loyalty in the telecommunications sector, possibly due to the high-involvement nature of telecommunications services. These findings have significant implications for telecommunications providers in emerging markets. The strong relationship between marketing mix elements and performance metrics suggests that companies should invest in comprehensive marketing strategies that address all four elements while paying particular attention to service quality and distribution efficiency. The demographic variations in response patterns indicate the need for segmented marketing approaches that consider customer characteristics and preferences.

The research findings also contribute to the theoretical understanding of marketing mix effectiveness in service industries, particularly in emerging market contexts. The validated measurement model and established relationships provide a framework for future research in similar markets and sectors. While the study provides valuable insights into marketing mix effectiveness in Iraq's telecommunications sector, several limitations warrant consideration. The cross-sectional nature of the data collection restricts causal inferences about the relationship between marketing mix elements and organizational performance over time. The sample, while adequate ($N=462$), predominantly represented urban areas (67.5%) and higher-educated consumers (81.2% with bachelor's or graduate degrees), potentially limiting generalizability to rural and less-educated populations.

Methodological limitations include potential common method bias, as data collection relied solely on self-reported measures from customers. The study's focus on customer perceptions excluded important operational metrics and internal company data that could provide a more comprehensive understanding of performance outcomes. Additionally, the research timeframe (four months) may not have captured seasonal variations in telecommunications service usage and customer behavior patterns. The geographic concentration in Iraq presents both a strength and limitation, as findings may not directly translate to other emerging markets with different regulatory environments, competitive landscapes, and cultural contexts. The study's emphasis on traditional marketing mix elements (4Ps) might have overlooked emerging digital transformation factors and technological disruptions affecting the telecommunications industry.

These limitations give rise to future research directions. Longitudinal studies can better explain causality and examine the temporal relationships that surround the use of the marketing mix and its performance effects. Researchers should explore the combination of objective performance measures with perceptual measures, combining financial data with indicators of operational efficiency and customer behavior analyses.

Comparative studies across several emerging markets help generalize the findings and tease out market-specific factors impinging on the effectiveness of the marketing mix. Exploring the extended marketing mix-7Ps in a context of digital transformation might contribute insights related to the development of new service delivery models. Another promising avenue involves the role of customer co-creation and service innovation in the optimization of marketing mix. More granular analysis of the demographic determinants influencing marketing mix effectiveness could bring segment-specific strategies for action. Future studies should again consider how changes in regulatory environments, technology, and competitive landscape influence the effective

implementation of marketing mix actions. Also, research into the aspect of service quality and organizational performance from both customer and employee viewpoints could provide a further holistic perspective. Researchers should also look into the interrelationships among marketing mix elements and operational efficiency metrics, especially in the context of emerging technologies such as 5G and IoT. Research on the role of organizational culture and change management in the implementation of marketing mix strategies would provide insights valuable to practitioners. Last but not least, investigation into sustainability considerations in marketing mix strategies is one of the important avenues for future research in the telecommunication sector.

6. Concluding remarks

This research has focused on the relationship between organizational performance and marketing mix elements in the telecommunications sector in Iraq. The findings have illustrated that all the elements of the marketing mix showed strong correlations with performance measures; however, the impact was stronger for product/service quality ($r = 0.634$, $p < 0.01$). The regression model illustrated that marketing mix elements explained 62.3% of the variance in organizational performance.

Distribution efficiency rated highest among marketing mix elements ($M = 3.91$), and price competitiveness, the lowest deep into analysis, scored at ($M = 3.45$), indicating further scope of improvement. Key metrics like market share (+4.3%), customer retention (+6.7%), and revenue growth (+4.5%) after-implementation results showed some outstanding positive variations. Demographic variables especially age and education exert a significant moderating impact.

These findings call for the telecommunications companies to adopt fair marketing strategies in which both service quality and competitive pricing structures are the main focus. This research contributes to the theoretical framework and practical implications of marketing mix strategies within developing telecommunications markets, hence setting a foundation for further research and industry applications.

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